

WAYS OF ORGANIZATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF ETHNO-TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN

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ANNOTATION

The article reveals the concept of ethno - tourism, its importance in the field of tourism and specific aspects. Possibilities and prospects of development of ethno tourism are analyzed.

Keywords: *ethno-tourism, tourist villages, tourist infrastructure, traditional culture.*

Uzbekistan is a unique country, where the oldest civilizations and cultures arose, developed, and it has become a country with great tourism potential, which is one of the best places for recreation and travel in the world in terms of its attractiveness. Today, there are more than 7,000 rare historical monuments, magnificent and unique examples of architecture in our country. Beautiful villages and national parks of our country are masterpieces of its rich and colorful nature. Tourism is a multi - faceted industry, and it is important to preserve its diversity. To see the world with your own eyes, to get acquainted with everyday life, customs and traditions of other peoples is an important component of ethno-tourism.

Ethnographic tourism - one of the booming tourism industries in modern Uzbekistan. Ethnographic tourism includes visits to places that allow to demonstrate the past, present, national culture, lifestyle, cultural identity of a certain group of people. The purpose of ethnographic tourism is to study the lifestyle of a particular nation or people and their specific characteristics. Today, when many elements of traditional culture are disappearing, its scientific study and popularization is undoubtedly one of the urgent issues of the day. We see this in the scientific works of a number of foreign and domestic scientists on ethno-tourism. For example, we can see in the scientific works of Carmen Babaita, Gabriela Sipos, Panikarova Svetlana, Shchukin Andrei, Barluka Antonina, as well as in the scientific articles of young researchers such as Soatova Sabokhat, Gilicheva Orzigul, Gaffarov Shohrukh, Eleonora Mirzadzhonova. The study, Takes into account the expected innovation changes in the coming years in determining the processes of development of ethno-

tourism and thus uses the methodology of studying the development of tourism infrastructure in general, as well as the method of determining the direction of development of components of tourism infrastructure through such methods as observation, comparison, empirical, research, systematic and offered a comparative analysis.

In 2022, more than 5.2m foreign tourists visited Uzbekistan. This is 2.9 times more than in 2021, and 2.5 million more than the plan for 2022. The volume of exports of tourism services in January-December 2022 exceeded 1.61 billion US dollars.

In 2022, 21.6 trillion UZS will be allocated for all investment projects in the tourism sector, and it is expected that by the end of the year 727 projects will be implemented and 22,901 new jobs will be created.

Advertising the opportunities of existing tourist settlements in the region, bringing tourism services in line with market demand, the organization of the market of tourism services internationally in the context of the modernization of the economy are one of the important tasks.

Firstly, according to international organisations and institutions, most forms of tourism are growing at an average rate of 5% a year, while ethno-tourism is growing at an average annual rate of 20-30%. Scientific experience and conclusions of many specialists and researchers show that despite the fact that ethno-tourism is a new and young direction of tourism, its popularity develops 2-3 times better than other tourist destinations;

Secondly, Uzbekistan has formed a base of certain achievements and experience in such types of tourism as historical tourism, religious tourism, cultural and educational tourism;

Thirdly, about 800 tour operator companies, about 600 hotels, more than 30 specially protected natural areas (reserves, national parks, rare natural monuments, etc.), 60 forestries are currently operating in Uzbekistan. There are also more than 100 tourist villages in Uzbekistan.

The main objective of the development of ethno-tourism is as follows:

- to demonstrate the ethnotourist potential, natural potential and opportunities of Uzbekistan in the world market of tourist services;
- Encourage research aimed at making more effective use of the ethnotourist resources and capacities of the regions, especially the villages;
- To encourage scientific research aimed at making more effective use of the ethnotourism resources and capacities of the regions, especially the increased importance and share of ethno-tourism in the development of tourism;

- a fundamental improvement in the quality of ethno-tourism services in the sphere of tourism activity introduced in Uzbekistan, and a rapid increase in the volume of ethno-tourism services;

- creation of scientific, innovative and methodical developments aimed at the development of ethno-tourism in the future;

Such types of tourism as historical tourism, religious tourism, medical tourism, cultural and educational tourism are mainly conducted in urban areas, where there is sufficient tourism infrastructure and facilities of service, and ethnotours are conducted mainly in nature and in villages, most ethnotours are characterized by traditions and crafts of the inhabitants of the region. Certainly, it is advisable to develop and deploy a number of system works in this direction.

Regions and areas where the state program for the development of ethno-tourism is not developed, the financial support of the state for the development of ethno-tourism is much less.

No statistical reporting on ethno-tourism facilities and visits to ethno-tourists is carried out;

In the development of ethnotourism, the relevant authorities and enterprises are not connected to each other, as well as the disorganized management of ethnotourism infrastructure;

The methods of organizing ethnotourism and socio-economic and organizational mechanisms for organizing ethnotourism have not been developed.

Ethno-tourism services are not at international level;

Lack of development of material and technical base of ethnotourism;

Absence of interaction and exchange of international experience in ethnotourism.

The potential of development of ethno-tourism of our country is extremely great, there are all opportunities for its rapid development. Only these potentials and opportunities need to be used wisely, based on the experience of countries that have developed ethno-tourism in the world, and implemented without errors on a scientific basis. These problems are identified only after we started to develop tourism and ethno-tourism in our country. Any area that has begun its development will achieve its perspective step by step.

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